

Timurids Eternal Garden Art

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ABSTRACT: This article examines the modern urban planning situation and the most important role of water in the artistic solution of architecture. When we talk about a park, we must know "where we are from and where we are going." Human and nature must create divine harmony. One of these divine landscape elements is water. She is not only the source of life, but also the pinnacle of aesthetic pleasure.

KEY WORDS: Merv, Banokat, Chorbog, hexagonal, canal, dynasty, reflection, paradise.

INTRODUCTION

It is known from history that Amir Temur was a strong politician, an unparalleled commander. In addition, he paid great attention to the independence and prosperity of the country and the peace of the people. In particular, he rebuilt ancient cities, such as Samarkand, Bukhara, Termez, Merv, Banokat (Shohrukhiya), a number of fortresses and fortresses, which were destroyed by the Mongol invasions [1].

THE MAIN RESULTS AND FINDINGS

It should be noted that Amir Temur celebrated every triumphant and joyful event with the construction of a magnificent architectural monument and garden. One of the gardens he created was Chorbog, which sets him apart from other gardens. Historical sources state that 12 parks were built in Samarkand [2].

Reconstruction of Chorbog. By D.Nozilov.

One of the best gardens was the Garden of Sultan Hussein Boykaro Nakhshi-Jahonaro ("Garden to decorate the world").

The garden area is divided into geometric shapes - triangular, square, hexagonal, with flower beds, alleys, ornamental and fruit trees. A well-thought-out system was used to move trees, shrubs, and flowers. When choosing flowers, the timing of flowering is noteworthy - because in the gardens there are always flowers in bloom. With this, people at that time tried to create gardens of paradise [3].

In the gardens, the irrigation system and various water facilities played the biggest role. Canals, ponds, pools, stepped waterfalls are subject to a certain regular plan. The turning of rivers and streams is alien to the aesthetics of the East. The accuracy of the form is valued here. As a rule, the shape of the pools is strictly geometric - polygonal, circular, rectangular. In addition to fruit and ornamental trees in the gardens, a special place is allocated for various flowers and greenery.

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The successors of the Timurid dynasty also carried out creative work in India. India's natural conditions and flora are diverse, as well as very rich. One of the characteristic features of the gardens is the extensive development of water systems, as well as the fact that the gardens are becoming an ensemble appearance in the water.

The most famous mausoleum in India is the Taj Mahal in Agra (1630-1652). King Jahan named it after his wife Orzumandbonu (Mumtoz Mahal) and built it for his indelible memory. Here the mausoleum is located at the foot of the garden and is built along the river, the back side of which is surrounded by a mountain. As a result, he embodied the idea of a mausoleum-garden [4].

Taj Mahal. India 1630-1647

Labi Haus. Uzbekistan 1569

later used in other countries of the world. In 1569, the Labi House complex was built in Bukhara, Uzbekistan.

In this way, Islam demonstrates its high philosophical views. Looking at the beautiful building on the water, he describes it as "a mortal world in which everything looks beautiful, but real life is before God." Although the following architectural monuments differ in geographical location, political and economic status, built in different centuries, architectural, planning compositional solutions, shape, size, environmental design, decoration, raw materials, color, they are unique ideas. the fantasy of building on water, as well as the curb of the building's reflection in the water.

**Comeres. Spain.
1360-1380**

**Lyabi Houz. Uzbekistan
1569**

**Taj-Mahal. India.
1630-1647**

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The Islamic landscape differs from other garden philosophies in that it remembers its garden of paradise and likens the gardens of this earth to the gardens of paradise in a figurative sense.

Uzbekistan did not lose its methods in construction and horticulture even during the Soviet era. On the contrary, it has evolved over time.

Independence Square Fountain. Opera and Ballet Theater named after Navoi.

In the first stage of modernization, first of all, the compatibility of the building or structure with the environment, its proximity to the buildings is taken into account. It requires a complex solution in harmony with residential buildings, the environment, taking care not to disturb the compositional scale and placing them in harmony with the buildings [5].

Nowadays, modern residential and garden design is developing and showing new styles. Housing environment as an integrated environment of urban life is formed by various functional and spatial elements: housing environment, cultural and household services, the environment of industrial complexes, recreation areas.

Tashkent City 2020 y.

In the 21st century, Timurid-style Chorbogs are of interest not only to locals but also to foreigners. Experts from major European countries, such as Britain, France and Spain, are interested in such gardens.

One of them is Manuel Nuse Yanovsky and Yulia Suprunovich de Nuse. Founded in 2017, the company has completed several projects in a short period of time. The company's projects are currently being implemented in European cities such as Paris, Barcelona, Dijon, Manyanville. This team provides advice on landscape design and landscape architecture, Business and Management Services, and urban planning projects.

Tashkent. The inner garden of Paradise is the Crystal Mosque

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Part of the gate to the heavenly Qur'an

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we can say that in all periods, in all countries, the original work of art has not lost its value and is passed down from generation to generation. Only such works of art appear in a fresh, modern look. That is why the garden art of the Timurids also lives on forever.

In the implementation of landscape design in the countries of the East there are the use of natural raw materials, aesthetic vision, philosophical approaches. In Western gardens, the philosophical view that "man is superior to nature" is put forward, and the view of the garden is formed on the basis of geometric shapes. The history of landscape design of Eastern and Western settlements has been studied and their peculiarities have been identified.

In Central Asian gardens, it is described as a "paradise", the compositional solution is symmetrical and reflects the image of a fantastic paradise. Although the philosophical views of the East and the West on the formation of landscape design were contradictory, it became clear that the gardens of Central Asia connected the two continents in a certain sense.

REFERENCES

- 1) The Art of gardens in East K.D. Rahimov, A.S.Uralov.
- 2) Sadykova, A. S. Uralov, Monograph: Central Asian Traditional Garden Style and Modern Garden-Park Art.
- 3) Ch. Edited by H. Agustin Nunez Alhambra under the microscope 2011.
- 4) Gardening art Baburids by S.N. Sadykov.
- 5) Pugachenkova G.A. The architecture of Central Asia in the 15th century. - Tashkent: Publishing house of literature and art. G. Gulyama, 1976 S.N.

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